

MANAGEMENT OF SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF PEDAGOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826837>

Abstract: This article discusses the specific features of managing and controlling the innovative activities of an educational institution.

Keywords: Education, innovation, management, student, teacher, system, science. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On improving the system of state administration for the development of scientific and innovative activities” dated April 1, 2021 No. PF-6198 and Resolution “On measures to further improve state policy in the field of science and state administration in innovative development” dated April 1, 2021 No. PQ-5047 set out tasks based on the specifics of implementing innovative activities of educational institutions in our country, its importance and necessity. The processes of creating and implementing innovations in the implementation of innovative activities of an educational institution also consist of certain cycles. From this point of view, the innovation process is a set of activities that are consistent in time dimensions, are functionally distinct from each other, acquire a separate content at different stages of the same importance. The application of fundamental ideas and knowledge that serve as the basis for innovation leads to the following results: - identification of unpromising projects and making the right decision; - further improvement of the innovative idea in the process of implementing it in practice; - the ability to adapt the innovation to the technological characteristics, the nature of the systems responsible for management and organizational activities. The functions of the use of financial resources of the innovative potential are: - ensuring the receipt of financial resources required for the introduction of innovations; - creating conditions for the appropriate provision of financial resources for innovative processes; - improving the implementation of innovative processes; - creating conditions for the creation and stimulation of innovations; - to promote the creation of innovative projects that meet various needs related to the functional activity and development of the existing innovation system; - to ensure the optimal cost and efficiency of innovative projects. Y. Schumpeter defines the following functional tasks of entities operating in the innovation sector: - to carry out commercial analysis in order to identify potential consumers interested in adopting innovations; - to search for authors of promising ideas, sources that provide opportunities for functional activity; - to organize the processes of creating innovations and putting them into practice; - to support the implementation of innovations into practice.

- at the stage of materialization of new ideas discovered in science, improving innovative work in the field of innovative activity;

The teacher should purposefully organize interpersonal relationships in the group at the stage of team formation. To do this, he must have a highly developed communicative approach and ability to establish relationships and contacts, and understand the students. According to S.V. Kondrat'eva, there is a certain correlation between the level of

understanding of the teacher and the impact he has on them. In a teacher with a high level of understanding, the character-forming effect comes first, while in a teacher with a low level of understanding, the disciplinary effect comes first. If the teacher does not pay enough attention to the organization of the activities of students, he will have to spend a lot of time and effort to maintain discipline. A positive attitude towards the personality of students and a system of incentives are an important part of the effectiveness of pedagogical communication. The content and criteria of effective incentives (according to P. Massen, J. Konjer, etc.) are as follows:

1. Encouragement is carried out regularly.
2. The teacher explains what exactly is worthy of encouragement.
3. The teacher looks with interest at the success of students.
4. The teacher encourages the achievement of certain results and explains the essence of this to students.
5. Teaches students to organize their work in order to achieve good results.
6. The incentive of each student should correspond to the effort he has expended.
7. The teacher connects the achieved result with the effort expended on him and indicates that such success can be achieved in the future.
8. After completing the previous task, he tries to arouse interest in the new task.
9. Draws the attention of students to the fact that the high level of mastery depends on the full use of the capabilities of these students.

The teacher fulfills his official duty to manage the educational process in the process of pedagogical dialogue innovation. In this sense, the teacher's relationship with the student is similar to the relationship of the boss with his subordinate, and the teacher can use the same methods used by the leader in managing it. When implementing the innovation process, it is necessary to emphasize the specifics of the work of the teacher (or leader) and the student (performer). The teacher manages several teams and the educational work being performed (lecture, laboratory work, practical training, seminar, etc.). As a result of managing several teams, the time spent working with each of them is relatively small. This innovative nature requires the teacher to work intensively on the study of individuals and groups. Motivation of teachers in educational institutions for mutual cooperation and mutual assistance is also of great importance. Motivation is distinguished by two types: - Motivation for success; - Motivation for fear of failure. Motivation for success has a positive character. The actions of learners are directed to achieve good results. Personal activity has an impact on the success of educational innovation.

Any educational institution that seeks to maintain its viability in market conditions must ultimately create some kind of innovation in the field of science or in the personnel training system, implement new ideas, that is, materialize ideas and sell them to potential buyers in the markets. The establishment of the activities of educational institutions on a commercial basis may, of course, distract them from their functional tasks to some extent, but engaging in scientific and innovative activities ultimately creates the opportunity for educational institutions to become financially self-sufficient. Along with the creation of an innovative environment operating on the scale of our republic, the activation of the innovative activities of educational institutions has become an objective need. The processes of creating and implementing innovations also consist of certain cycles. From this point of view, the innovation cycle is a set of activities that continue consistently in time dimensions, acquire a

functionally separate content at different stages of equal importance and differ from each other. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6108 dated November 6, 2020 on measures to develop the spheres of education and science in the new period of development of Uzbekistan sets out the tasks based on the features of the introduction of innovative activities of educational institutions in our country, its importance and necessity. Also, in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 No. PQ-4884 "On additional measures to further improve the education system", tasks on improving the quality of education are separately identified for each link of the continuous education system, and the organization of the educational process based on the use of educational technologies is also important for the implementation of these tasks. The innovations introduced into practice will ultimately be recognized by society. In this regard, we would like to highlight the following global trends:

Democratization of the education system, ensuring continuity and integrity at all stages of the education system, strengthening the independence of educational institutions. 2. Creating equal opportunities for all segments of the population to receive education. 3. Socio-economic development sets new tasks for education. The development of education for professional study, not for future work, but for one's own personal needs, etc. Their implementation should be based on the following principles of development of innovative education. • Ensuring the interdependence of education and practice, preparing personnel for practical work; • Widely introducing scientific achievements into education: • Ensuring the continuity and coherence of education, lifelong learning; • Ensuring corporate cooperation of graduates, forming and developing the traditions of educational institutions; • Combining education and upbringing, educating high moral qualities; • Educating intelligentsia with high spiritual qualities. Prospects for implementing innovations in educational processes: • Modernization of the material and technical base of educational institutions, effective use of the capabilities of information and communication technologies in the educational process, introduction of distance learning. • Regional and international integration of educational institutions, development of international cooperation in the field of education;

The role of innovative technologies in the development of education. The future of every society is determined by the level of development of the education system, which is an integral part and a vital necessity. Today, the reform and improvement of the continuous education system of our country, which is moving along the path of independent development, has risen to the level of state policy, raising it to a new qualitative level, introducing advanced pedagogical and information technologies into it, and increasing the efficiency of education. With the adoption of the Law "On Education" and the "National Program for Personnel Training", the basis for training modern personnel through the continuous education system was created. As is known, continuity and coherence in the education system, first of all, expands the spiritual and intellectual potential of society, and also ensures the sustainable development of production as a factor in improving the social and scientific development of the state. The development of pedagogical technologies and their introduction into the educational process, as well as the rapid exchange and improvement of information technologies, create an opportunity for each person to strengthen their professional training and skills. General pedagogical and didactic tools for all stages of education are aimed at improving the effectiveness of independent work of the student (or student) based on program knowledge, imagination and skills, increasing their

interest in scientific thinking, the subject of study, deepening their professional knowledge, and increasing their activity during theoretical and practical training. World pedagogical experience confirms that the potential of modern pedagogical technologies to interest students (or students) in subjects and increase their activity in independent work is unlimited. The task of education today is to teach students to operate independently in an increasingly information-educational environment, to use information flows rationally. For this, it is necessary to create a continuous environment and conditions for independent work for them. Accordingly, it would not be wrong to say that it is an urgent problem today to prepare general vocational subjects based on the needs and desires of young people through information and communication technologies and to try to form their knowledge and skills. Transition from traditional education to innovative education, Until now, in traditional education, students (or pupils) were taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge. Such a method stifled independent thinking, creative research, and initiative in students (or pupils). Nowadays, it is better to say that there is an interest in increasing the effectiveness of education using interactive methods (innovative pedagogical and information technologies) in the educational process. Attention to education is increasing day by day. Classes using modern technologies are aimed at helping students (or pupils) to search for the knowledge they are learning, independently study and analyze it, and even draw conclusions on their own.

The teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, knowledge and upbringing of the individual and the team in this process, and at the same time performs the function of management, guidance. In such a learning process, the student (or student) becomes the main figure.

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